

CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE COMBINED EFFICACY OF *PATOLADI KASHAYA* AND *DURVADI LEPA* IN THE MANAGEMENT OF *DADRU KUSHTA*: A CASE SERIES

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ABSTRACT

Skin is largest organ and outermost covering of human body. Because skin interfaces with the environment, it plays an important role in protecting body against pathogens and other environmental conditions. It's size and external location makes it susceptible to wide variety of disorders. In recent years, there has been a considerable increase in the incidence of skin diseases in the tropical and developing countries like India.^[1] Patients experience physical, emotional, socioeconomic embarrassment in society. Most of the skin diseases are caused due to bacterial or fungal infections. Poverty, poor sanitation, unhygienic conditions, pollution are some of the reasons for infections.^[1] In *Ayurveda*, skin diseases are explained under heading *Kushtha* which is considered one among the *Asthaumahagada*.^[2] *Lasika*, *Rakta*, *Mansa Dhatu*, *Twacha* are *Dushya* involve in *Kushtha*.^[3] *Twakvarna* and *Sparsha* are crucial in *Ayurveda* to understand the state of *Dhatu* and *Dosha* in *Shareera*. *Twaka* has placed great emphasis on the traits of *Rasadhatu Sarata* which are detailed in *Twakasarata*.^[4]

KEYWORDS: Skin, *Dadru*, Dermatophytosis, *Patoladi kashay*.

INTRODUCTION

Dadru Kushtha is *Pittakaphaj* phenomenon.^[5] Clinical features of *Dadru Kushtha* are *Kandu*(itching) *Raga*(erythema), *Pidika*(eruption), *Utsanna mandala*(elevated circular skin lesion).^[6] As per modern perspective *Dadru Kushtha* disease can be correlated as “Superficial

fungal infection of skin”.^[7] Tinea or ringworm infections are a group of very highly infectious segmented fungal infections, and are characterized by circular lesions usually with sharp margins and raised edges.

WHO states the prevalence of superficial mycotic infections between 20%-25%.^[8] Due to changing lifestyle, dietary inconsistencies, environmental factors like humidity the incidences of skin disease are increasing day by day. There are several *Yogas* in *Ayurveda* for the management of *Dadru Kushtha*, which include *Antarparimarjana* and *Bahirparimarjana*. *Antarparimarjana* includes *Shaman* and *Shodhan Chikitsa*.

Now a days due to busy life schedule individual prefer *Shaman Chikitsa*, which can be prescribed at OPD level. As it will be simple convenient and also cost effective. Combination of *Bahirparimarjana Chikitsa* and *Shaman Aushadhi* will be more effective in patients so present study is based on combined effect of *Bahirparimarjan* and *Shaman Aushadhi*. I have selected *Patoladi Kashaya*^[9] as *Antarparimarjan Chikitsa* and a *Durvadi Lepa*^[10] as *Bahirparimarjan Chikitsa*, the ingredients present in the formulation (*Patoladi Kashaya*) are *Patola*, *Katukrohini*, *Madhustrava*, *Chandan*, *Guduchi*, *Patha*. which have *Kushthaghna*, *Kandughna*, *Raktashodhan* properties, and *Durvadi Lepa* are *Durva Churna* and *Haridra* which have *Krimighna* and *Kandughna* properties which both results in *Sampraptivighatan* of *Dadru Kushtha*. In present case study 6 patients of *Dadru Kushtha* were taken in view of inclusion criteria, in which *Patoladi Kashaya* was internal medicine and *Durvadi Lepa* as external application.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Aim and Objectives: To Evaluate the combine efficacy of *Patoladi Kashaya* and *Durvadi Lepa* in the management of *Dadru Kushtha*.

Centre of Study: SSNJ hospital Solapur.

1. Diagnostic criteria

1. *Kandu* (itching)
2. *Pidika* (eruptions)
3. *Raga* (erythema or redness)
4. *Utsanna Mandala* (elevated skin lesion)

2. Inclusion criteria

1. Subjects with classical sign & symptoms of *Dadru* i.e *Kandu*, *Pidikotpatti*, *Raga*, *Utsanna mandala*.
2. Subjects of either gender and age group between 18 to 70 yrs irrespective of religion, occupation and socio-economic status will be selected.
3. Subjects having symptoms of *Dadru Kushtha* within the time period of 6 month.

3. Exclusion criteria

1. Subjects who are suffering from any other type of skin disease like Herpes zoster, eczema.
2. Subjects who are suffering from any other known case of systemic Diseases i.e. Uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus etc.
3. Pregnant and lactating women.
4. Subjects taking immunosuppressive medications.

4. Criteria of assessment

Subjective criteria^[11]

1. *Kandu* (Itching)
2. *Pidika* (Eruptions)
3. *Raga* (Erythema)
4. *Utsanna Mandala* (Elevated patches)

Sr. no./Parameters	Grade 0	Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3
1. <i>Kandu</i> (Itching)	Absent	Mild	Moderate	Severe
2. <i>Raga</i> (Erythema)	Absent	Faint reddish skin	Red Coloured skin	Reddish brown skin
3. <i>Pidika</i> (Eruptions)	Absent	1 – 3 <i>Pidika</i>	4 – 7 <i>Pidika</i>	>7 <i>Pidika</i>
4. <i>Utsanna Mandal</i> (Elevated Patches)	Absent	Mild elevation	Moderate elevation	Severe elevation

Objective criteria^[12]

1. Size of lesion
2. Number of lesion. (In specified area and body part)

Gradation For Objective Parameters

Sr.no	A) Size of Lesion	Grade
1.	No lesion	0
2.	<5cm ²	1
3.	5-10cm ²	2
4.	10-15cm ²	3
5.	>15cm ²	4

It is calculated according to size of lesion of specific area trace on butter paper and counted that area with the help of graph paper.

Sr no.	B) No. of Lesions	Grade
1.	No lesions	0
2.	0-5 lesions	1
3.	5-10 lesions	2
4.	10-20 lesions	3
5.	All over the body	4
6.	All over the body, face and merged with each other	5

Chikitsa

1. Patoladi Kashaya

पटोलकटुरोहिणीचन्दनं मधुस्रवगुडूचिपाठान्वितम्।

निहन्ति कफपित्तकुष्ठज्वरान्विषं वमिमरोचकं कामलाम् ||अ.ह.सू. 15/15

Sr.no	Name of Dravya	Latin name	Useful part	Quantity	Swarupa
1	Patola	<i>Trichosanthes dioica Roxb.</i>	Patra	2.08gm	Bharad Churna
2	Katurohini (kutaki)	<i>Picrorhiza Kurroa Royle ex Benth</i>	Mula/ Bhoumika Kanda	2.08gm	Bharad Churna
3	Chandan	<i>Santalum album Linn.</i>	Kandasar, taila	2.08gm	Bharad Churna
4	Madhustrava (Murva)	<i>Marsdenia tenacissima</i>	Mula	2.08gm	Bharad Churna
5	Guduchi	<i>Tinospora Cordifolia Willd Miers ex Hook f. and Thomas</i>	Kanda	2.08gm	Bharad Churna
6	Patha	<i>Cissampelos pareira Linn.</i>	Mula Bhoumika kanda	2.08gm	Bharad Churna

Dravya and it's properties

Dravya	Rasa	Veerya	Vipak	Guna
Patola ^[13]	Tikta, Katu	Ushna	Katu	Laghu, Ruksha
Katurohini ^[14] (Kutaki)	Tikta	Ushna	Katu	Ruksha, Laghu
Chandan ^[15]	Tikta, Madhura	Sheeta	Katu	Laghu, Ruksha
Madhustrava ^[16] (murva)	Tikta, Kashay	Ushna	Katu	Guru Ruksha
Guduchi ^[17]	Tikta, Kashay	Ushna	Madhura	Laghu Snigdha
Patha ^[18]	Tikta	Ushna	Katu	Laghu Teekshna

Durvadi lepa

दुर्वानिशायुतो लेपः कच्छूपामाविनाशनः।

क्रिमीदद्दूहरश्चैव शीतपित्तापहः स्मृतः॥ च.द. 51/6

Sr no	Name of Dravya	Latin name	Useful part	Quantity	Swarupa
1	Durva	Cynodon dactylon Pers.	Patra, Moola	1 part	Churna
2	Nisha (Haridra)	Curcuma Longa Linn.	Kanda	1 part	Churna

Dravya and it's properties

Dravya	Rasa	Veerya	Vipak	Guna
Durva ^[19]	Kashay, Madhura	Sheeta	Madhura	Laghu
Haridra ^[20]	Tikta, Katu	Ushna	Katu	Ruksha

Kashaya Preparation (Decoction)

Part of *Bharad Churna* (mixed in equal quantity) is taken and 16th part of water with reference to *Bharad Churna* has been added to it. The heat will be given to the mixture till it remained to 1/8th of total (48ml).

- Dose: 48 ml *Kashaya* twice in a day
- *Aushadhi Sevan Kala: Pashchatbhakta (Vyan Udan Kala)*
- Route of Administration: oral
- Duration: 45 days
- Follow up: Every 15th day

Guidelines for Lepa application

1. Mix *Lepa Dravya* with water.
2. Make semisolid mixture.
3. Apply *Lepa* over affected area (till it dry up) in once a day for 45 days duration
4. Thickness of lepa 1/4th of *Anguli* of patient
5. Time :- once daily
6. Duration:- 45 days
7. Follow up:- after every 15 day

Pathyapathya^[21]

Pathya - Dadim, Mudga, Patola, Draksh, Karvellaka, Nitya snan, Mrudu Vastra dharana,

Koshataki.

Apathya- Anupa Mamsa, Divaswapa, Atapasevana, Paryushit Ahara, Harit shak, Masha, Dadhi.

Follow up and outcome

After completion of treatment there was mark improvement in signs and symptoms i.e. in *Kandu* (Itching), *Raga*(erythma), *Pidika*(eruptions), *Utsanna Mandala*. No any *Vyapada* (complications) during full course of treatment and during follow up was seen. On follow up after 45 days, patients were satisfied with the management. There was 84% relief in the previous symptoms.

<i>Lakshana</i>	Patient 1		Patient 2		Patient 3		Patient 4		Patient 5		Patient 6	
	BT	AT										
<i>Kandu</i> (Itching)	3	0	3	0	2	0	3	0	3	0	3	0
<i>Raga</i> (Erythema)	3	0	3	0	3	0	3	1	2	0	3	0
<i>Pidika</i> (Eruptions)	2	0	3	1	3	0	2	0	3	0	3	1
<i>Utsanna mandala</i> (Elevated patches)	3	0	2	0	3	1	2	1	3	0	3	0
Size of <i>Mandala</i>	3	1	2	1	2	0	3	0	3	0	2	1
No. of lesion	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	1

BT- Before Treatment, AT-After Treatment Pictures

FIG.1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

DISCUSSION

Dadru is a *Kapha–Pitta* predominant disorder and is classified under *Aupsargika Roga*. *Nidana-parivarjana* and strict adherence to *Pathya-Apathya* play a crucial role in its management. Among the treated patients, four showed early positive outcomes, which can be attributed to their proper compliance with the advised *Pathya-Apathya*.

The administered *Kashaya* demonstrated significant relief in *Kandu* due to its *Tikta-pradhāna Rasa*, *Ushna Vīrya*, *Kapha-Pitta-hara*, and *Kuṣṭhaghna* properties. *Pidika* formation occurs due to *Kapha-Pitta pradhana Tridosha* involvement, and the *Ushna*, *Ruksha*, and *Tikshna Gunas* of the *Kashaya* helped in reducing these lesions.

Maṇḍalas develop as a result of *Tridosha* vitiation along with involvement of four *Dushya Dhatus*. The *Kuṣṭhaghna*, *Tvakdoshahara*, *Raktadoshahara* properties, along with *Laghu* and *Ruksha Gunas* of the *Kashaya*, contributed to the reduction of *Mandalas* in *Dadru*.

Mode of action of *Patoladi Kashaya*^[22]

All the drugs of *Patoladi Kashaya* are collectively of *Tikta Rasa*, digestive and used in *Pitta* disorders.

Patola due to *Tikta Rasa* and digestive property acts on *Kushtha* and removes *Kleda* from channels. It acts on vitiated *Kapha* and works as pacify in other associated diseases related with *Rakta* and *Pitta*.

Katurohini is recognized by name '*Asuri*' in *Vedic* period. It is used for treating *Kushtha* and *Shvitra* and other skin disorders. Due to *Tikta Rasa* and *Sheeta Virya* it act as pacify specilly on *Pitta Dosha*. After digestion of *Rasaraktagat Dosha*, due to its *Bhedan* [drastic purgative] action it removes vitiated *Dosha*.

Chandana being *Ruksha Gunatmak* is used for absorption of *Kled*. *Tikta* and *Madhura Rasa* and *Sheeta Virya* of *Chandan* used to stop further vitiation of *Vata Dosha*.

Madhustrava being *Tikta* in *Rasa* helps in pacify *Pitta* and act as appetizer, purify the blood; *Ushna Virya* helps in absorb *Kleda*.

Tikta Rasa and *Ushna Virya* of *Guduchi* pacify all three *Dosha*, absorb the *Kleda*, and purify the blood.

Due to *Tikta Rasa* and *Ushna Virya* it acts as purify the blood and absorb the *Kleda*. It has wound healing property. It pacifies *Pitta* and act as digestive.

Patoladi Kashaya mainly contains *Tikta-kashaya Rasapradhana*, *Laghu-Ruksha Guna Pradhana*, *Katu Vipaki* and *Ushna Veerya Dravyas* i.e., *Patola*, *Katurohini*, *Chandana*, *Madhusrava*, *Guduchi* and *Patha*. *Patoladi Gana* is Tridoshagna in nature, especially *Kapha-pitta Shamak*. *Patola* with its *Madhur Vipaka* and *Ushna Guna*, *Guduchi* with its *Snigdha* and *Ushna Guna* and *Patha* and *Murva* with its *Ushna Veerya* pacifies *Vata*. *Kutaki* and *Chandan* due to *Tikta Rasa* and *Sheeta Veerya*, *Patola* and *Patha* due to *Tikta Rasa* while *Guduchi* with its *Tikta*, *Kashaya Rasa* pacifies *Pitta Dosha*. So, this drugs of this *Gana* can be given in diseased condition where *Pitta* and *Kapha Dosha* are predominant in the pathogenesis. Thereby helps in *Samprapti Vighatana* and regain the equilibrium of *Doshas*.

Dravyas of *Patoladi Gana* possess *Dhatwagnideepan*, *Dhaatuprasadak*, *Aampachan*, *Strotoshodhan*, *Raktashodhak*, *Bastishodhak* and *Vishaghna* properties, hence it can be effective in *Dadru Kushtha*.

Mode of action of *Durvadi Lepa*

Durva, possessing *Kashaya–Madhura Rasa*, *Sheeta Virya*, *Madhura Vipaka* and *Laghu Guna*, exerts *Pitta-Shamaka*, *Dahahara* and *Kledaghna* actions. Its *Kashaya Rasa* helps in *Kleda Shoshana* and *Sthanik Sankocha*, thereby reducing *Utsanna Mandala* and *Raga*, while *Madhura Vipaka* supports *Twak Sthiratva* and *Ropana*.

Haridra, having *Tikta–Katu Rasa*, *Ushna Virya*, *Katu Vipaka* and *Ruksha Guna*, acts as *Kapha-hara*, *Kandughna* and *Krimighna*. *Tikta* and *Katu Rasa* help in *Srotoshodhana* and *Lekhana* of vitiated *Kapha*, while its *Ushna Virya* counteracts *Kapha-Sanga* and *Picchilata*, leading to relief in *Kandu* and *Pidika*.

The combined application of *Durva* and *Haridra* in *lepa* form results in *Kaphapitta-Shamana*, *Kledaghna*, *Kandughna* and *Tvak-shodhana* effects at the local level. Thus, *Durvadi Lepa* effectively interrupts the *Samprapti* of *Dadru Kushtha*, leading to reduction in itching, erythema and lesion activity.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, the combined use of *Patoladi Kashaya* and *Durvadi Lepa* showed significant improvement by the end of the treatment period. The skin, being the outermost

and most visible organ of the body, plays a vital role in protection as well as aesthetic appearance; therefore, early and appropriate management of skin disorders is essential for a favorable prognosis.

Considering the changing lifestyle patterns and the increasing resistance and recurrence observed with certain contemporary treatment modalities, there is a growing need to emphasize *Ayurvedic* interventions that address the disease at the level of *Dosha* and *Dushya*. *Patoladi Kashaya*, owing to its *Tikta-Kashaya Rasa*, *Kaphapitta-Shamaka* and *Rakta-Shodhana* properties, helps in correcting *Rakta Dushṭi* and *Kleda*, which are key factors in the pathogenesis of *Dadru Kushtha*.

Durvadi Lepa, when applied locally, exerts *Kandughna*, *Kledaghna*, *Krimighna* and *Dahahara* actions, providing symptomatic relief and facilitating *Samprapti-Vighatana* at the site of lesion.

Thus, the combined systemic action of *Patoladi Kashaya* and local effect of *Durvadi Lepa* results in effective management of *Dadru Kushtha*, with minimal chances of recurrence and without significant adverse effects.

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